

Research on issues and countermeasures of role model education for junior high school students in the era of artificial intelligence

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Abstract

In the new context of the era of artificial intelligence, exemplary education remains significantly important for junior high school students. Therefore, the issues currently present in exemplary education and how to improve them hold considerable research value. This paper defines relevant concepts through studies and theoretical foundations related to exemplary education both domestically and internationally. Current exemplary education for junior high school students exhibits new characteristics. Through an analysis of the current situation, it identifies the existing problems in exemplary education for junior high school students. In response to these issues, it conducts a multifaceted cause analysis and proposes targeted strategies, aiming to provide references for enhancing the effectiveness of exemplary education for junior high school students in the era of artificial intelligence.

Keywords: The era of artificial intelligence; middle school students; exemplary education

1. Introduction

The purpose of this study is as follows: First, to understand the new characteristics of role model education for junior high school students in the era of artificial intelligence, and to conduct an in-depth analysis of the current state of role model education among junior high school students under the widespread application of artificial intelligence technology, in order to identify the practical issues in current role model education for junior high school students. Second, theoretical research results must be implemented in practice to demonstrate their practical value. After identifying existing problems, specific cause analyses should be conducted, and more targeted solutions should be proposed to enhance the effectiveness of role model education for junior high school students. This can help students establish correct views on role models and leverage the role of role models in promoting their healthy growth and all-around development.

The significance of this study lies in its important theoretical implications. On one hand, analyzing the current situation and problems of role model education for junior high school students under the background of artificial intelligence, summarizing its characteristics, helps to form an objective theoretical system based on subjective perception. On the other hand, reflecting on the results obtained and proposing future development suggestions for role model education contributes to forming more feasible and scientifically effective guiding theories. The study also has significant practical implications. On one hand, during the investigation and research process, it enhances understanding and attention to role model education for junior high school students. On the other hand, the conclusions drawn from the analysis of role model education for junior high school students can provide certain references for future research, better addressing the issues in role model education for junior high school students under the new era background, thus

providing correct guidance for role model education for junior high school students and allowing role model education to fully play its role in their development.

2. Literature Review

Current State of Domestic Research

In modern Chinese, '榜' refers to notices or lists that are posted publicly, while '样' means 'something used as a standard'. Combining '榜' and '样', it can be interpreted as: something published for reference by everyone, serving as a standard, whether it is an outstanding person or deed. This aligns with the definition of role models in modern Chinese dictionaries: 'role models are exemplary good people or deeds worth learning from'. There are numerous papers on the theme of 'role models', primarily focusing on 'role model education' and 'the power of role models', with secondary themes including 'role model demonstration' and 'role model education'. These studies are mainly distributed across disciplines such as 'higher education' and 'educational theory and management', predominantly consisting of applied research.

Definitions of 'role models' in relevant literature include: Some scholars represented by Peng Huaizu define role models as exemplary figures established by mainstream culture, who exhibit outstanding qualities in values, worldviews, and life perspectives. The existence of role models represents cultural strength and the spirit of the times (Peng, 2006). Other scholars represented by Zhang Rufen believe, to some extent, that role models are specific behaviors demonstrated by individuals in practical activities, which contain certain spiritual cores. These behaviors serve as templates for other social members to imitate and learn from, possessing motivational value that inspires and uplifts (Zhang, 2008). In summary, role models refer to individuals or specific actions that excel in certain aspects and are worth learning from, setting positive standards for learners, providing positive influence and motivation.

Mentorship education refers to an educational practice that uses role models to enhance the qualities of learners. The literature on mentorship education primarily focuses on middle school and college students, often examining its impact within specific historical contexts and applying it across various disciplines, with a particular emphasis on ideological and political education. Definitions of mentorship education by scholars include: According to Wen Jingjing, mentorship education is a socially oriented activity with clear goals. During this process, educators, based on the psychological and physical development laws of learners, utilize role models or their deeds to purposefully, plannedly, and organizedly guide learners to form moral qualities and value systems suitable for a specific stage of social development (Wen, 2011). Zhang Yangle views mentorship education as a transformation from traditional didactic and indoctrinative methods to activities that evoke genuine emotional resonance and self-identification among learners. Learners actively imitate and practice. In his perspective, mentorship education fundamentally serves as value education, aiming to cultivate specific moral qualities and social atmospheres (Zhang, 2017). Yang Ruiping and Wei We believe that mentorship education involves establishing role models according to certain moral standards and ideals, using vivid personal images and deeds as educational tools. Through specific methods and means, it aims to set exemplary figures and motivate progress (Yang & Wei, 2015).

In summary, mentorship education is a social practice that uses role models as carriers, enabling learners to accept value systems and behavioral norms through imitation and learning, thereby shaping their personalities.

The current era is the age of artificial intelligence. There are 5,740 related studies on the theme of 'age of artificial intelligence,' covering various fields such as education, law, and industry, indicating that artificial intelligence has deeply penetrated all sectors. The age of artificial intelligence not only signifies technological innovation but also

represents a profound social transformation. Therefore, when exploring the essence of the age of artificial intelligence, it is necessary to consider multiple dimensions(Wang, 2024).

In the field of education, the extensive application of artificial intelligence leads to significant adjustments in employment structures, giving rise to a series of new professions related to artificial intelligence. To cultivate talents suited for the age of artificial intelligence, educational models must undergo reform. In terms of interpersonal interactions, artificial intelligence alters people's modes of social interaction. Social media platforms leverage artificial intelligence to offer personalized content recommendations, greatly influencing how people access information and communicate. Virtual social interactions are gradually emerging, allowing individuals to engage in social activities in virtual spaces through virtual reality and augmented reality technologies. Additionally, the age of artificial intelligence brings numerous challenges, with the security and reliability of artificial intelligence systems being particularly concerning. A malfunction or malicious attack could lead to severe consequences.

Current state of foreign research

Bandura proposed that children's social behavior is primarily acquired through observing and imitating the behaviors of individuals in real life. Practical evidence shows that imitation is an inherent trait of humans, and the models children imitate play a crucial role in educational practices. Observational learning is the primary form of modeling for students, during which they acquire symbolic representations of the demonstrated activities and act accordingly based on these representations(Bandura,2014).

Some scholars believe that the key to exemplary education lies in the exemplary role model set by educators. Soviet educator Sukhomlinsky, in his book 'Suggestions to Teachers,' discussed the role of teachers in exemplary education, emphasizing and elaborating on the significant exemplary influence teachers have on their students(Sukhomlinsky, 1984).

3. Method

In accordance with the needs of the research topic, review and analyze relevant literature and books on the selection of role models by junior high school students. Understand the current state of research on clear role models, role model education, and the effectiveness of role model education to lay the foundation for the research topic. At the same time, address the shortcomings of existing studies by synthesizing reviewed materials and personal views to propose reasonable suggestions.

4. Results

Through literature review, it has been found that there is extensive research on role models and role model education both domestically and internationally, forming a rich theoretical system. There is also a considerable amount of research on the effectiveness of role model education. Domestic studies mainly focus on college students and high school students, while research involving middle school students in the era of artificial intelligence is relatively scarce.

Role model education is widely applied in educational fields. The importance of role model education for middle school students' growth holds significant value and meaning, and enhancing the effectiveness of role model education for middle school students in the era of artificial intelligence is of great significance. Therefore, the author believes that conducting investigation and research on the existing issues of role model education for middle school students in the era of artificial intelligence, analyzing and summarizing them, can better play the theoretical guiding role of role model education for middle school students, thereby promoting their healthy physical and mental development.

This research topic will build upon previous studies related to role model education, extensively learn and study research ideas and methods, strive to more accurately summarize the characteristics of role model education for middle school students in the era of artificial intelligence, analyze the problems and improvement strategies of role model education for middle school students in the new era, and hope to provide assistance for the guidance and education of role model education for middle school students.

5. Discussion

Defining related concepts

Role Model: From etymological perspective, in ancient Chinese, '榜' describes tools used to assist in correcting bows and crossbows. The 'Shuo Wen Jie Zi' mentions '榜, used to assist bows and crossbows, from wood and body.' In modern Chinese, combining '榜' with '样' can be interpreted as: publicly announced for reference, serving as a standard, whether it's an outstanding person or deed.

In related studies, the concept of role models has been given different meanings. For example, some scholars consider role models as exemplary figures established by mainstream culture, heroes who exhibit outstanding qualities in values, worldviews, and life perspectives, representing cultural power and the spirit of the times. Role models are also defined as specific behaviors demonstrated by individuals in practical activities, embodying certain spiritual cores, providing imitation and learning templates for other social members, and possessing motivational value to inspire and uplift.

In summary, this paper defines role models as individuals or actions that excel in certain aspects, exhibiting specific behaviors or qualities worth learning, setting positive standards for learners, and providing positive influence and motivation.

Role Model Education: At its essence, education is a practice aimed at promoting goodness. Role model education can be understood as enhancing the quality of those being educated through role models. There are numerous studies on role model education. In related research, role model education is defined as a socially oriented practice with clear goal orientation, or a transformation from indoctrinative educational methods to activities where learners genuinely resonate emotionally and identify with the role models. Role model education is also defined as establishing role models based on certain moral standards and ideals, using vivid personal images and deeds as educational carriers, employing certain methods to achieve the purpose of setting examples and motivating progress. There are various expressions of role model education, but essentially they are similar. In summary, this paper defines role model education as a social practice where the educated learn values and behavioral expressions through imitation and learning from role models, thereby achieving self-improvement.

Artificial Intelligence Era: The 'Artificial Intelligence Era' refers to a historical stage driven by general-purpose AI and strong AI technologies, leading to systemic changes in societal production, lifestyle, and civilization forms. Its essence lies in humans achieving autonomous perception, cognition, and decision-making capabilities outside their bodies for the first time at the technological level, forming a new social operation paradigm centered on algorithms. The 'Artificial Intelligence Era' is not merely a technical periodization concept but a complex process of interplay between technological breakthroughs and adaptive social changes. It represents the first time humans have extended their autonomous perception, cognition, and decision-making abilities externally at the technological level, forming a new social operation paradigm centered on algorithms.

Relevant theoretical foundation

Bandura's observational learning theory: Observational learning involves learning by observing the behaviors of others (models) and their consequences. This theory posits that most of an individual's behavioral patterns are acquired through observing model behaviors. Learners can learn by observing whether the outcomes of others' behaviors are rewarded or punished.

Bandura suggests that learners must first pay attention to the model's behavior before subsequent learning can occur. In model education, efforts should be made to attract the learner's attention. The learner needs to store the observed model behavior in memory either as images or verbal representations for future retrieval. Educators should guide learners to deeply understand and process the model behaviors. After memorizing the model behaviors, learners attempt to replicate these behaviors in real-life situations. This implies that model education should not remain at the theoretical level but should provide learners with opportunities for practice. Whether learners exhibit behaviors learned from models depends on their expectations and motivations regarding the outcomes of these behaviors. Positive feedback and reinforcement should be provided promptly in model education.

In model education, learners observe the behaviors of models and subsequently imitate these behaviors, internalizing them as their own behavioral patterns. This process involves more than just mimicking surface actions; it also includes understanding and internalizing the underlying meanings of the behaviors.

The significant importance of role model education for junior high school students in the era of artificial intelligence

Mentorship education has a long history in educational history and plays a significant role in students' growth. In the era of artificial intelligence, mentorship education for junior high school students also plays an important role.

Cultivating New Era Talents: Different eras have different requirements for talent cultivation that fully reflect the characteristics of the times. In the era of artificial intelligence, talent cultivation should demonstrate new features such as comprehensiveness, digitization, and internationalization. The goal of China's education is to cultivate builders and successors of socialism who are well-rounded in morality, intelligence, physical fitness, aesthetics, and labor. It aims to develop individuals with ideals, abilities, and a sense of responsibility, possessing an international perspective and actively integrating into international exchanges.

Mentorship education, as an important method of moral education, can effectively enhance students' moral qualities. Besides improving moral qualities, modern mentorship education expands the scope of selecting role models, establishing role models in various aspects such as morality, intelligence, physical fitness, aesthetics, and labor. This helps students form the habit of active learning and promotes the balanced development of all five areas, thereby better enhancing students' comprehensive quality.

The role models chosen in mentorship education are mostly contemporary pioneers. Apart from typical deeds and excellent moral qualities, these role models also fully demonstrate the spirit of the times and align with the trend of social development. This not only helps improve students' moral qualities but also aids them in integrating into society and keeping pace with the times.

Enriching Moral Education Methods: Mentorship education, as an important method of moral education, has been widely used in cultivating students' moral education since ancient times. For teaching work itself, the application of mentorship education in the teaching process in the new era enriches moral education methods and improves educational quality. Compared to other moral education methods, mentorship education is irreplaceable, characterized by its authenticity, practicality, and emotional appeal.

Unlike traditional didactic moral education, mentorship education is more flexible, free from temporal and spatial constraints. It can select materials from students' actual lives or draw from excellent traditional Chinese culture or international culture, making the content rich and real. In the context of contemporary value pluralism, abstract moral preaching is easily perceived as empty slogans. Role models, through specific deeds, concretize qualities such as 'dedication' and 'perseverance,' effectively countering the nihilistic spirit emerging in the new era.

Mentorship education conveys moral concepts through specific figures and deeds. Role models often have strong persuasive power. Mentorship education demonstrates behavior choices in real-life scenarios, providing reference examples. Compared to pure theoretical teaching, it can evoke deep-seated emotions within people, making it easier to translate into concrete actions. This makes teaching more specific and vivid, fully mobilizing students' enthusiasm and enhancing teaching effectiveness.

The characteristics and mission of role model education for junior high school students in the era of artificial intelligence

In the era of artificial intelligence, characteristics such as diversification, intelligence, informatization, technologization, distinctiveness, life integration, and personalization are evident. Middle school students also exhibit new stage-specific traits, and exemplary education for middle school students in the new era displays diversified, intelligent, and personalized features and missions, which are specifically reflected in the stages and elements of exemplary education.

Characteristics of the Era of Artificial Intelligence: Currently, we are in the era of artificial intelligence, which is a brand-new era that not only integrates traditional era characteristics but also showcases potential future societal features, including diversification, intelligence, informatization, technologization, distinctiveness, life integration, and personalization (Ji, 2018). The specific manifestations of the era's characteristics in the age of artificial intelligence are as follows. Artificial intelligence technology benefits various industries, presenting a characteristic of technological inclusivity. The reduction in technological barriers allows AI applications to permeate all levels of production and life. In the field of education, teachers and students utilize AI to generate PPTs and employ algorithms for precise analysis of learning situations. Human-machine collaboration in the era of artificial intelligence continues to deepen. The current cohort of middle school students, as 'digital natives,' manage their lives through voice assistants, receive algorithm-customized services, and socialize and entertain in virtual reality. The cooperation between humans and artificial intelligence has transcended the level of tool assistance, moving towards jointly completing complex tasks. However, the double-edged sword effect of artificial intelligence is also significant: on one hand, it can effectively enhance efficiency; on the other hand, it may lead to issues such as privacy breaches, algorithmic bias, and deepfakes. These problems necessitate continuous strengthening of technical literacy, emphasis on human-machine collaboration capabilities, and the establishment of inclusive policy frameworks.

Characteristics of Middle School Students in the Era of Artificial Intelligence: Middle school students are currently at a critical period of growth, requiring meticulous cultivation. The middle school stage extends from the higher grades of elementary school and connects to high school, being a crucial period for nurturing ideological morals and forming correct worldviews, outlooks on life, and values. In the era of artificial intelligence, various societal thoughts and cultures interweave, significantly increasing the channels through which students access information. Student development exhibits independence, diversity, and distinctiveness. Middle school students' curiosity and exploration of artificial intelligence. Middle school students show a strong interest in artificial intelligence, driven by curiosity to actively understand and learn about AI technologies. With the widespread use of smart devices, middle school students become increasingly proficient in using electronic devices such as smartphones and tablets. They

quickly familiarize themselves with various applications, including AI-related ones like intelligent voice assistants and online learning platforms.

Changes in students' learning abilities and methods. Artificial intelligence technology provides possibilities for personalized learning, allowing middle school students to choose suitable learning resources and paths based on their learning progress and interests. Besides developing autonomous learning skills, middle school students also need to learn how to collaborate with others in learning.

Characteristics and Mission of Role Model Education for Middle School Students in the Era of Artificial Intelligence

Diversification of Role Model Education for Middle School Students: The content of role model education for middle school students should be diversified. Besides traditional role models such as historical figures and moral exemplars, the era of artificial intelligence has brought forth many new role models from various fields and backgrounds, closely related to the new age. Different students have different criteria for selecting role models. To better meet the diverse needs of students, the content of role model education should not be limited to a specific field. When selecting educational content, it should be chosen from multiple perspectives to achieve diversification of role model education content. The educational methods for role model education for middle school students should also be diversified. Traditional role model education mainly involves classroom lectures and organizing the viewing of images or videos, which is relatively monotonous. In the era of artificial intelligence, role model education can leverage technology, using virtual reality to create realistic scenarios, and implementing online role model education to achieve diversification of educational methods.

Intelligence of Role Model Education for Middle School Students: The teaching methods of role model education for middle school students should be intelligent. Traditional role model education primarily relies on lectures, which cannot meet the diverse needs of students and is outdated. The era of artificial intelligence provides technological convenience for the 'online and offline integration' teaching method, promoting the implementation of role model spirit and effectively improving teaching efficiency. The integration of resources for role model education should also be intelligent. The era of artificial intelligence is characterized by a rapid increase in data, making the resources for role model education rich and diverse. Relying on network data, role model education can break through spatial and temporal limitations, integrate high-quality role model resources, and form an open and shared digital resource library.

Personalization of Role Model Education for Middle School Students: Role model education for middle school students should be targeted. Previous role model education typically aimed at student groups, neglecting individual uniqueness. In the era of artificial intelligence, role model education can deeply analyze each student's characteristics to enhance the targeting of education. Students need to develop autonomous learning abilities. Autonomous learning ability is an important quality for students. In the era of artificial intelligence, middle school students increasingly understand and use AI technology, enhancing their autonomous learning capabilities. Students can actively explore role model materials around them, choose role model figures autonomously, and continuously develop their autonomous learning abilities.

Issues in role model education for junior high school students in the era of artificial intelligence

The results of current role model education for junior high school students mostly remain at the level of understanding and recognition, manifesting as understanding the behavior of role models and the background of such behavior, as well as a sense of identification with the actions and spirit of role models. However, most students find it difficult to practice these behaviors in their studies and daily lives.

Outdated Content of Role Model Education: The content of role model education significantly impacts its outcomes. In the era of artificial intelligence, the content of role model education is continuously enriched, and students' autonomous awareness gradually increases, demanding higher quality content due to their independent thinking and critical abilities. However, the current content of role model education updates slowly, making it hard for students to truly identify with it. Artificial intelligence has brought significant changes to information dissemination and acquisition methods. Traditional role model education materials, such as paper books and conventional teaching videos, are relatively monotonous and outdated. Most role model cases focus on historical figures and moral exemplars, resulting in lagging educational content that inadequately explores new-age role models, failing to meet the demands of the AI era and causing a disconnect between role model education and contemporary needs, thus failing to effectively stimulate student enthusiasm. There are differences among regions, schools, and individual students, making standardized role model educational resources difficult to meet personalized learning needs. They cannot precisely cater to each junior high school student's interests, learning styles, and cognitive levels. The current role model education selects content based on past student characteristics and standards, which often diverges from students' real-life experiences and genuine needs. In the AI era, role model education should better consider students' personalized needs.

Monotonous Forms of Role Model Education: Role model education is a form of social practice activity. The advancement of role model education in the AI era lies in using technology to improve teaching methods, but the forms of role model education remain relatively monotonous, leading to superficial 'formalism'. This 'formalism' refers to surface-level learning of role model behaviors without deeply understanding their spirit and qualities (Wang & Du, 2025). In the AI era, role model education for junior high school students still primarily relies on classroom lectures. Teachers present the deeds and virtues of role models on stage while students passively listen. This single lecture format lacks interaction and interest, making it challenging to fully engage students' initiative and enthusiasm. For example, during moral education classes, teachers might spend considerable time reading stories about exemplary individuals, but due to the monotonous approach, many students may lose focus, making it difficult for them to deeply understand the spirit of role models. In the AI era, role model education often combines multimedia with lectures, delivering content through simple and mechanical preaching. Frequently, role model education only stays at the level of reading out role model deeds, which is quite fixed, making it hard for students to emotionally resonate. This limits students' understanding of role models to the surface level, preventing them from deeply appreciating the underlying spiritual strength of role models.

Analysis of the Causes of Role Model Education Issues for Junior High School Students in the Era of Artificial Intelligence

Mentorship education is widely applied in actual teaching processes. In the new context of the AI era, mentorship education faces issues of weakened effectiveness, which can be generally attributed to the selection of role models and the specific methods of implementing mentorship education.

Stagnation in Updating Mentorship Education Content: The mentorship education in the AI era exhibits characteristics of diversification, intelligence, and personalization, with its content also showing diverse and personalized traits. However, due to the diversified development of society in the AI era leading to collisions of value concepts, there are differences in the definition and demand for role models, making it difficult for mentorship education content to meet the new needs of junior high school students in the AI era. The stagnation in updating mentorship education content fails to reflect the features of contemporary development. Junior high school students are developing individuals who are curious about societal changes and have diverse needs. The role models established in mentorship education for junior high school students under the AI era do not reflect the new characteristics of AI

development, causing students to lose interest in the uniform mentorship education and fail to achieve expected outcomes.

The selection of mentorship education content overlooks the students' contemporary characteristics. The role models currently established in junior high school mentorship education typically excel in a particular field but are distant from students' real lives. Students' understanding of these role models usually comes from textual or video introductions, lacking detailed knowledge, making it hard for them to comprehend and identify with these figures, thus neglecting the students' central position in mentorship education and reducing their enthusiasm. Moreover, student development is stage-based, with different characteristics at various stages. Junior high school students have enhanced logical thinking and judgment abilities, but they struggle to understand the more abstract ideological concepts exhibited by role models. Sometimes, mentorship education emphasizes the spirit of role models to highlight themes, overly conceptualizing and abstracting the image of role models, creating a sense of detachment(Guo, 2023).

The forms of exemplary education overlook new technological advantages: The implementation of exemplary education involves educators acting as intermediaries between themselves and those being educated, significantly impacting the outcomes of exemplary education. In the era of artificial intelligence, advanced technological means offer more possibilities for exemplary education, but its current application of AI technology remains limited. For instance, AI can analyze big data to understand each student's interests and cognitive characteristics, providing personalized exemplary education content. Virtual reality technology can also be used to allow students to experience the life scenes and struggle of role models firsthand, enhancing the directness and appeal of education. However, most schools and educators have not fully tapped into the potential of these technologies, still primarily using traditional lecture-based methods for exemplary education. During the process of exemplary education, online educational resources are not sufficiently explored or utilized. The internet offers abundant exemplary educational resources, such as various themed online courses, interviews with exemplary figures, interactive forums, etc., but these resources have not been effectively integrated and fully utilized. Many schools and teachers are accustomed to traditional textbooks and lesson plans, and are not adept at guiding students to utilize online resources for autonomous learning and interactive communication, leading to the wasteful idling of these valuable educational resources.

Improvement strategies for role model education of junior high school students in the era of artificial intelligence

Mentorship education in the era of artificial intelligence holds significant value for student growth and social development. Addressing the current issue of weakened effectiveness in mentorship education, one can start by selecting suitable role models and improving the implementation methods of mentorship education to effectively enhance its efficacy in the new era.

Enriching the content of mentorship education: In the age of artificial intelligence, junior high school students have access to more information and learn about more outstanding individuals, making the selection of role models more diverse. Students' expectations for their role models are also higher. During the process of mentorship education, it is essential to clearly define the criteria for selecting role models from multiple aspects, and the content of mentorship education should align with the genuine needs of students. The content of role models should be continuously updated to reflect the characteristics of the times, considering the real needs of junior high school students in the age of artificial intelligence. This ensures that the content of mentorship education keeps pace with the development of the times. By deeply exploring the connotations of the era, selecting outstanding representatives from emerging industries, and incorporating new role models into mentorship education, the content of mentorship education can be optimized and adjusted. It is crucial to strengthen the identification and selection of authentic and credible role models in mentorship education. In the era of artificial intelligence, the emergence and development of virtual culture have brought virtual characters into students' view. Role models must be real, and their stories and qualities must be authentic and credible, aligning with the cognitive characteristics of junior high school students, allowing them to understand, accept, and

practice these role models consciously. When promoting role models, avoid false propaganda, combining macro and micro perspectives, and focusing on the deeds of role models during their youth. Mentorship education should match the developmental stages of students, interpreting role models from multiple angles to create a realistic, three-dimensional, credible, and approachable image of role models(Xie & Liu, 2023).

Role models should be diverse. The diversified and personalized characteristics of mentorship education in the era of artificial intelligence require that the content of mentorship education be continuously enriched in line with the development of the times. Different students have different personality traits and cognitive levels, leading to varying demands for role models. By establishing different role models, we can reflect the diversification of social development, encouraging students to become independent and autonomous individuals in the new era.

Utilize artificial intelligence to enrich teaching formats

To enhance the effectiveness of role model education and address the issue of its monotonous methods, effective approaches need to be adopted. The era of artificial intelligence provides more convenient and diverse ways for implementing role model education, which can transcend time and location constraints and be integrated into subject teaching and practical activities. Utilize artificial intelligence technology to achieve personalized instruction. The AI era offers conditions for personalized teaching by using technological means to collect data and analyze students' individual characteristics. Artificial intelligence can generate personalized role model education materials based on each student's learning progress, interests, and cognitive traits. It can also develop targeted teaching strategies to meet students' diverse needs. The implementation of role model education must rely on practical activities, combining AI technology with such activities. Using technologies like 'VR', create realistic teaching scenarios to make role model education flexible and vivid, allowing students to experience the power and influence of role models in real situations, thereby enhancing their learning motivation and sense of social responsibility. Encourage students to emulate role models in behavior, helping them internalize values and moral qualities and manifest them in actions. The implementation methods of role model education should continuously evolve with the times and students' needs, leveraging AI technology to enrich educational forms, making the implementation of role model education more aligned with the diversified, intelligent, and personalized features and missions of middle school role model education in the AI era, thus better improving the teaching effectiveness of role model education.

References

- Bandura, A. (2014). *Social learning theory*. Renmin University of China Press. (Original work published 1977)
- Guo, S. (2023). *Research on role model education for college students in the new era* (Doctoral dissertation, Northeast Normal University). CNKI. <https://doi.org/10.27011/d.cnki.gdbsu.2023.000719>
- Ji, T. T. (2018). *Research on role model education for children in the intelligent era* (Master's thesis, Henan University). CNKI.
- Peng, H. Z. (2006). The coupling of role model education and idol worship. *Journal of Nantong University (Social Sciences Edition)*, 22(5), 1–6.
- Sukhomlinsky, V. A. (1984). *Advice for teachers (D. K. Du, Trans.)*. Educational Science Publishing House. (Original work published 1969)
- Wang, F., & Du, D. S. (2025). Dilemmas and solutions of role model education in the new media era. *Media Forum*, 8(1), 114–117.

- Wang, Y. D. (2024). *Research on innovation of ideological and political education methods in the era of artificial intelligence* (Doctoral dissertation, Central China Normal University).
- Wen, J. J. (2011). *Research on the contemporary value and realization of role model education* (Master's thesis, Hebei Normal University). CNKI.
- Xie, X. M., & Liu, J. (2023). Path optimization of role model education for college students in the new era. *School Party Building and Ideological Education*, 18, 45–47. <https://doi.org/10.19865/j.cnki.xxdj.2023.18.012>
- Yang, R. P., & Wei, W. (2015). Analysis of role model education in the new media era. *China Higher Education*, 19, 30–32.
- Zhang, R. F. (2008). On the effectiveness of role model education. *Journal of Shanxi Normal University (Social Science Edition)*, 35(4), 12–16.
- Zhang, Y. L. (2017). Role model education from the perspective of modernity. *Guizhou Social Sciences*, 338(10), 100–104. <https://doi.org/10.13713/j.cnki.cssci.2017.10.016>

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